

Total Pancreatectomy and Islet Cell Auto Transplantation in A Patient with Situs Inversus: Anatomical Navigation and Surgical Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Background: Total pancreatectomy and islet cell auto transplantation (TPIAT) is a technically demanding operation. Recurrent episodes of pancreatitis create a hostile environment, complicating the dissection of the peripancreatic tissue planes during procurement of the pancreatic gland. In this setting, safe access to the portal venous system and isolation of splenic vein for infusion of the viscous islet graft becomes challenging. Situs inversus totalis (SIT) is a rare congenital condition often accompanied by abnormal vascular anatomy affecting the portal venous system. Studying the vascular anatomy before TPIAT is crucial for safe intraoperative navigation even in complex scenarios like the one presented here of a successful TPIAT on a background of SIT with absent spleno-portal confluence.

Case Presentation: A 30-year-old lady with a background of Kartagener syndrome was diagnosed with chronic recurrent pancreatitis. After extensive work up, she was found to be eligible for TPIAT. Interrupted inferior vena cava, polesplenia, splenic vein hypoplasia, absence of spleno-portal confluence along with pre-duodenal portal vein and early bifurcation at the level of the superior border of the pancreas, were the anatomical variations identified in pre-operative imaging studies. Intraoperatively, difficult dissection of the peripancreatic planes was made further challenging by the non-conventional mesenteric vascular anatomy. In view of absence of spleno-portal confluence, an alternate route for islet infusion was mandatory. The early bifurcation of the portal vein facilitated infusion of the islet graft through the left portal branch. Following the completion of islet graft infusion, the vessel was reconstructed, maintaining adequate perfusion to the left lobe of the liver. No postoperative complications were observed.

Conclusion: SIT is a rare genetic anomaly often accompanied by multiple anatomical abnormalities with highly variable abdominal vascular anatomy. Careful preoperative mapping of the vascular anatomy in this group of patients plays a key role when complex hepato-pancreato-biliary procedures and operations are planned. In this case, it allowed safe navigation during surgical dissection and mandated islet infusion through the left portal vein without thrombotic complication. TPIAT is a complex procedure performed at specialized centres with extensive surgical expertise to manage intricate clinical situations.

Keywords: Situs inversus totalis; Kartagener syndrome; Total pancreatectomy; Islet cell auto transplantation; Interrupted inferior vena cava and Portal vein thrombosis

INTRODUCTION

Total pancreatectomy and islet cell auto transplantation (TPIAT) is a well-established complex hepato-pancreato-biliary procedure for a very selected group of patients.

TPIAT is indicated for a specific subset of patients with chronic pancreatitis of hereditary, idiopathic or other aetiologies. This group of patients experience debilitating chronic pancreatic pain that significantly diminishes their quality of life, necessitating frequent hospitalizations. Moreover, they exhibit an elevated risk of developing pancreatic cancer compared to the general population. The primary objective of the procedure is to improve overall quality of life, while potentially mitigating the risk of postoperative diabetes mellitus [1,2].

The procedure entails resection of the entire pancreas along with the duodenum and common bile duct as well as the spleen. After safe gland procurement, the pancreas is isolated and processed in the lab producing the islet graft. The final and crucial step of the operation is to gain safe access to the portal venous system, often via the splenic vein stump, to facilitate infusion of the auto- islet graft via a large bore catheter. The high viscosity of the graft is a well-known risk factor for portal vein thrombosis and underlies the importance of safe access to portal venous system [3,4].

Situs inversus totalis (SIT) is defined as the transposition of the abdominal organs mirroring anatomical placement across right and left body axis [5]. It is a rare entity affecting 1:10.000 individuals. SIT brings unique therapeutic challenges when surgical or interventional procedures are required due to the non-conventional anatomy noted in this group of patients [6,7]. While transposition of solid organs is relatively straightforward to recognize on imaging, delineation of vascular anatomy requires careful review. Specifically, interrupted inferior vena cava (IVC) and an anomalous portal venous system possess great challenge when hepato-pancreato-biliary surgery is planned in this group of patients [5,8,9].

We present the first case of TPIAT in a patient with SIT and absence of the spleno-portal confluence.

CASE REPORT

A 30-year-old lady with a background of SIT and primary ciliary dyskinesia (Kartagener syndrome) [10] was referred to our tertiary centre for recurrent episodes of pancreatitis. She also had history of Crohn's disease. Over a

period of fifteen years, the patient suffered multiple episodes of abdominal pain due to acute pancreatitis requiring hospital admission. Gallstone disease, alcohol intake, genetic mutations, hypercalcemia, hyperparathyroidism, autoimmune aetiology and pancreatic anatomical variants were all excluded as potential causes of her recurrent episodes of pancreatitis and her disease was considered idiopathic. She was referred to our tertiary centre for further assessment for TPIAT. The patient retained good glycaemic control while pancreatic exocrine insufficiency was well managed with pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy. After completion of work up and discussion in our specialised TPIAT meeting, a clear indication for the procedure was identified.

Investigations

The remainder of her medical, surgical, family history and physical examination was unremarkable. Laboratory tests were within reference range except for mild thrombocytosis with a platelet count of 1100/ μ l. Haematology opinion was sought and the finding was attributed to a recent episode of pancreatitis.

Imaging studies, with the first being a chest x-ray, revealed dextrocardia. A triple phase contrast enhanced computed tomogram (CT) was performed assessing the chest, abdomen and pelvis. The imaging confirmed dextrocardia and abdominal situs inversus with multiple vascular anatomical anomalies. Due to the complexity of the planned TPIAT procedure, detailed examination of the anatomy on imaging was mandatory.

The stomach was lying in the left side of the abdomen. The duodenal arch was lying on the right and the small bowel appearances were unremarkable. The large bowel was malrotated with the cecum lying in midline. The liver was occupying the entirety of the left and right side of the upper abdomen. The left liver was lying on the right side of the abdomen with the falciform ligament lying in the midline. The right liver was lying on the left side of the abdomen and the gallbladder was noted alongside the left midclavicular line (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Coronal CT of the Upper Abdomen: The liver is occupying the entirety of the upper abdomen and anatomically the right lobe is found on the left while the left lobe is lying on the right of the upper abdomen

The pancreas was lying on left abdomen, however, the gland had round shape with no identifiable head, neck, body or tail (**Figure 2**). There was no radiological evidence of recent pancreatitis on the preoperative imaging studies, however, peripancreatic tissue planes appear blurred owing to chronic peripancreatic inflammation.

Polysplenia was noted radiologically, with three distinct round structures lying in the left retroperitoneal space (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Axial portal venous phase CT highlighting the pancreas (arrow). The gland has a round shape with no identifiable head, neck, body and tail

Figure 3: Axial portal venous phase CT showing polysplenia (arrow). Three distinct round structures lying in the left retroperitoneal space

The portal venous system demonstrated significant anatomical variations. There was no distinct superior mesenteric vein (SMV) trunk. Multiple mesenteric veins were joining anteriorly to the pancreas soon before a major right and left prepyloric portal vein was noted with no shaped portal vein trunk. Both the main right and left portal veins were supplying the corresponding parts of the liver (Figure 4). Within the liver parenchyma, the left and right portal vein were communicating.

Figure 4: Coronal portal venous phase CT showing the portal venous anatomy: on the left image, left portal vein lying anteriorly; on the right image the right portal vein lying posteriorly

There was no inferior mesenteric vein noted and a small vessel representing the splenic vein was identified lying posteriorly to the pancreas. This was joining the left renal vein and both were draining into an interrupted semi-formed ‘lower’ inferior vena cava (IVC) lying on the left of the abdomen. Another vascular structure on the right retroperitoneal space represented the ‘upper’ IVC, in which the right renal vein, which was noted in the normal anatomical position, was draining into (Figure 5). There was no retro hepatic portion of the IVC and hepatic veins were draining into the right atrium, with the latter lying on the left, as the patient had dextrocardia.

Figure 5: Coronal portal venous phase CT showing the ‘upper’ part of the interrupted IVC. The right renal vein draining into right portion of the IVC

There was also variant arterial anatomy, but this had no surgical significance. A small calibre celiac axis gave rise to left gastric and splenic arteries and a replaced common hepatic artery arose from superior mesenteric artery.

Surgery

Meticulous study of the CT imaging delineated anatomy and aided surgical navigation intraoperatively. Moreover, taking into account the unconventional portal anatomy, alternative routes for islet infusion were identified. Potential access for islet transplantation were either the left portal vein extrahepatically or access to left portal vein via Rex recess or as a third option, the left gastric vein could be used which in this case was draining into the right portal vein branch.

After opening the abdomen, situs inversus was observed (Figure 6). After careful dissection of liver hilum, retrograde cholecystectomy and identification and division of main bile duct, the portal vein branches were isolated (Figure 7). The peripancreatic tissue planes were carefully dissected, the first part of the duodenum and jejunum were divided and the left end of the pancreas was dissected free towards the midline. The splenic structures were not visualised throughout the procedure. The final part of the specimen 's resection proved challenging as there was no identifiable SMV trunk and small bowel drainage was dissected and carefully preserved. After meticulous navigation through the planes, completion of total pancreatectomy along with the duodenum and bile duct was achieved and the specimen was sent to the lab to be further processed for islet isolation.

Figure 6: Intraoperative image of situs inversus: the right liver is lying on the left side of the abdomen with the gallbladder positioned alongside the left midclavicular line (arrow showing the gallbladder marking midclavicular line)

Figure 7: Intraoperative configuration of left and right portal branches. The prepyloric portal vein bifurcates low, at the level of superior border of the pancreas. The left portal branch lying anteriorly to the right

The surgical procedure continued with the reconstruction of the gastrointestinal tract via the formation of hepato-jejunosotomy and gastro-jejunosotomy anastomoses. Meanwhile, the resected specimen underwent processing to isolate and prepare the islet cell graft, a time-consuming process with a duration of approximately three hours.

The islet graft composed of 75,000 islets equivalents. The left portal vein was selected as the best option for the islet transplantation due to its adequate diameter. A 13 French vascular catheter was inserted in this vessel and islets were infused into the left liver lobe. The portal vein pressures were assessed pre-, during and post -infusion, as per standard practice. The portal pressure gradient was 8mmHg post infusion, a satisfactory level post islet transplantation. Upon completion of infusion, the catheter was removed leaving a large defect in the left portal vein occupying two thirds of its diameter. This was successfully reconstructed with 6/0 Prolene interrupted sutures. This was an essential step in an effort to preserve left portal flow, acknowledging the harbored higher thrombotic risk post islet transfusion that can occur in the early postoperative period.

The post operative course was uneventful. A CT scan postoperatively confirmed left portal vein patency (Figure 8). The patient was discharged after eleven days of admission with good overall glycemic control, however, requiring additional insulin, as expected due to the limited islet graft produced.

Figure 8: Coronal portal venous phase CT imaging showing the patent reconstructed left portal vein (arrow)

DISCUSSION

TPIAT is a technically challenging operation. The fibrotic tissue surrounding the peripancreatic planes create a hostile environment within the upper abdomen. Mesenteric dissection is hazardous and this plays a key role to the success of the operation which is aiming to gain safe access to portal venous system for islet graft infusion [11].

The high risk of portal vein thrombosis is a well described complication of this operation thus the selected access for islet cell infusion is a crucial step [11].

In this case, surgical expertise and skills were of paramount importance to avoid vascular compromise. Left portal vein isolation due to its low bifurcation made cannulation easier for islet infusion into the left lobe of the liver.

After islet graft infusion, reconstruction of the left portal vein was essential. Alternative options, such as sacrificing this major branch or choose alternate route for islet infusion, were deemed less favourable.

Visceral heterotaxy or situs ambiguus is defined as the abnormal arrangement of thoraco-abdominal organs across the right and left axis of the body. Heterotaxy with mirror image of the normal arrangement is called situs inversus or situs solitus. Heterotaxy is historically linked with asplenia or polesplenia [6,7,12]. This group of patients often demonstrate great variability of the abdominal vascular anatomy with interruption of IVC being the most common one encountered. Portal venous system anomalous anatomy is often noted in this group of patients. Subsequently, hepato-pancreato-biliary procedures mandate careful examination of anatomy prior to any intervention.

Addressing trauma in patients with SIT presents a unique challenge due to the rarity of the condition. Clinicians are not suspicious about the unconventional anatomy in the acute setting, fact that challenges further prompt diagnosis during clinical emergencies [14]. However, planned procedures offer an opportunity to identify SIT, enabling clinicians to prepare accordingly.

Liver transplantation [13], pancreatico-duodenectomy for resection of pseudopapillary pancreatic cancer or biliary cancer [13,15-18] and extrahepatic biliary tree excision for choledochal cyst have all been reported in patients with SIT [19-21]. Here we describe the first case of TPIAT in this patient cohort.

Meticulous surgical planning facilitates the advancement of surgical techniques, as evidenced by the documented cases of successful laparoscopic pancreaticoduodenectomy procedures performed on patients with SIT. This underscores the pivotal role of preoperative preparation in enabling surgeons to refine their skills and achieve favourable outcomes in complex cases that deviate from anatomical norms.

CONCLUSION

Patients with SIT have altered abdominal anatomy involving both solid organs but also portal venous vasculature. Thorough anatomical understanding and meticulous preoperative planning are imperative for successful hepato-pancreato-biliary procedures. TPIAT is a highly complex operation performed at specialized centres with extensive surgical expertise in managing intricate clinical scenarios to optimize outcomes.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Evangelia Florou made substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data analysis and interpretation of data, participated in drafting the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content and gave final approval of the version to be published and is designated as the guarantor.

Carol Balasingh made substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data analysis and interpretation of data.

Matthew J Seager made substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data analysis and interpretation of data, participated in drafting the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content and gave final approval of the version to be published and is designated as the guarantor.

Evangelos Prassas made substantial contributions to conception and design.

Parthi Srinivasan made substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data analysis and interpretation of data, participated in drafting the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content and gave final approval of the version to be published and is designated as the guarantor.

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